

EFFECT OF DAMPING ON THE ENERGY ABSORBING CAPACITY OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

S. J. Jalali and F. Taheri, Department of Civil Engineering, Technical University of Nova Scotia, Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada

ABSTRACT

The energy absorbing capacity of unidirectional 0° fiber reinforced composite beams subjected to impact loading is considered. Relations for evaluating the fracture initiation energy, including the effect of damping and inertia, are derived and presented. The derivation is based on the assumption that the phenomenon can be represented by a dynamic system with single degree of freedom. The proposed solution is used to analyze the impact response of several fiber reinforced composite beams. The calculated results compares very well with the published experimental values of other workers. The analysis shows that the damping has a significant influence on the values of impact fracture energy but the kinetic energy stored in the specimen is negligible. The reliability of our assumption concerning the proposed dynamic system is also validated by the finite element analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Impact resistance is an engineering quantity that plays a significant role in the design of reinforced polymer composites. In certain applications it may actually be the primary criterion for design. In terms of design variables, the fracture initiation and the fracture propagation energies are the most significant quantities. However, the commonly used impact test methods (such as Charpy and Izod) cannot evaluate these quantities, hence, a more elaborate testing procedure is necessary. Therefore, analytical solutions are desirable and are often used to evaluate these quantities.

Because of the short duration loading in low velocity impact, the effect of damping is usually neglected. In this paper it is shown that the effect of damping is important. Even in some composites the energy absorbed due to damping is larger than the strain energy.

To evaluate the energy capacity of composites, response of a simply supported beam under concentrated impact loading at midspan is considered. It is assumed that the impact will be applied by dropping a weight from a specified height. The response of the beam will be a function of the mass and velocity of the weight, and the beam stiffness and the mass. Charpy test on unnotched specimen produces the same situation. During the impact, it is assumed that behavior of the beam is linear. Therefore, with this assumption we will consider the energies in the beam up to the point that corresponds to the onset of the first nonlinearity due to fiber pullout, delamination, debonding and/or fiber collapse. To insure the validity of derived formulae a comparison is made with some experimental results.

FORMULATION

Fig. 1 shows the first three mode shapes of a simply supported beam under free vibration. Because of zero amplitude at midspan of the beam, mode 2 and all other even modes do not have any influence on the response of the beam when it is subjected to an impact load at its midspan. Furthermore, because of the concentration of striker mass at midspan which is much larger than the beam's own mass, the effect of the third mode and other odd modes are quite negligible.

Figure 1. Mode shapes of simply supported beam

As it is depicted in Fig. 2, with a reasonable degree of accuracy, our simply supported beam can be represented by a single degree of freedom (SDOF) system. In this figure, c is the damping constant. m_e denotes the equivalent mass of the beam at its midspan, and k is the beam's stiffness; m_w and v_w are the mass and the velocity of the striker, respectively.

Figure 2. Representation of impact of a simply supported beam with a SDOF system

Neglecting the damping effect, the total energy (sum of potential and kinetic energies) of the system at any time remains constant and is equal to the kinetic energy of the striker at the instant of contact with beam. This can be represented by:

$$\frac{1}{2} m \dot{X}^2 + \frac{1}{2} k X^2 = \frac{1}{2} m_w v_w^2 \tag{1}$$

where X is the displacement of system and $m = m_e + m_w$. Dot denotes the derivative with respect to time. The solution of this differential equation is,

$$u = \frac{\dot{X}(0)}{\omega} \sin \omega t \tag{2}$$

where $\dot{X}(0)$ is the velocity the system as a whole at $t = 0$, i.e., $\dot{X}(0) = \sqrt{m_w v_w^2 / (m_w + m_e)}$. ω is the natural frequency of the system and is the square root of k / m . Eqn (2) indicates that the response of our system, neglecting the damping effect, is equal to the response of an undamped

SDOF system under free vibration with initial velocity $\dot{X}(0)$. If we include the effect of damping into our system, by analogy, the equation of motion of our system becomes [1],

$$u = e^{-\xi\omega t} \frac{\dot{X}(0)}{\omega_D} \sin \omega_D t \quad (3)$$

and,

$$\dot{X} = -\xi\omega t e^{-\xi\omega t} \frac{\dot{X}(0)}{\omega_D} \sin \omega_D t + e^{-\xi\omega t} \dot{X}(0) \cos \omega_D t \quad (4)$$

where $\xi = c / (2m\omega)$, is damping ratio and $\omega_D = \omega\sqrt{1-\xi^2}$, is damped vibration frequency. For a small damping ratio there is not much difference between damped and undamped frequency. Also, since the load duration is minute, $\xi\omega t$ is very small hence, the difference between the values obtained from Eqn (3) and Eqn (2) is negligible. In this case Eqn (4) reduces to,

$$\dot{X} = \dot{X}(0) \cos \omega_D t \quad (5)$$

The energy that is absorbed by the system consists of three parts: strain or potential energy, damping energy and kinetic energy. Forces corresponding to each energy term can be determined by Eqn (6), (7), and (8), as follows:

$$F_s = kX \quad (6)$$

$$F_D = c \dot{X} \quad (7)$$

$$F_I = m_e \ddot{X} \quad (8)$$

Similarly, the energies corresponding to the above forces can be represented by:

$$V_s = \frac{1}{2} k X^2 = \frac{1}{2} F_s X \quad (9)$$

$$V_D = 2\xi\omega m \int_0^t (\dot{X})^2 dt \quad (10)$$

$$V_I = \frac{1}{2} m_e (\dot{X})^2 \quad (11)$$

Figure 3. Schematic view of forces and energies during a half cycle of vibration

The characteristics of Eqn (6) through (11) are shown schematically in Fig. 3. During impact, prior to F_S reaching to its maximum value, the process of failure begins. Consequently, due to the onset of nonlinearity the above equations will no longer govern. However, the slope of the F_S curve can still remain positive. It should be noted that the total applied force on the specimen at any time is the sum of F_S , F_D , and F_I .

In beams with large L/h ratio, failure begins in flexural mode and is accompanied by fibers breakage. However in short beams, shear failure would occur first. In the case of flexural failure mode, deflection at the onset of first ply failure for a simply supported specimen with a rectangular cross-section is,

$$\delta = \frac{1}{6} \frac{\sigma_{\max}}{E'} \frac{L^2}{h} \quad (12)$$

where h is the depth of beam and E' is the equivalent modulus of elasticity. The effect of shear is included in this modulus by,

$$E' = \frac{E}{1 + 1.2 \left(\frac{h}{L}\right)^2 \frac{E}{G}} \quad (13)$$

where E and G are the Young's and shear moduli of the material, respectively. Equating Eqn (12) to Eqn (3) or Eqn (2), yields the value of the failure initiation time (t_i). Velocity at t_i is shown by \dot{X}_i , and can be calculated by Eqn (5) or more accurately by Eqn (4). Substituting displacement and velocity in Eqn (9) through (11), the following equations are obtained.

$$V_s = \frac{\sigma_{\max}^2 L b h}{18 E'} \quad (14)$$

$$V_D = \xi m \omega \left[\delta \dot{X}_i + \dot{X}(0)^2 t \right] \quad (15)$$

$$V_I = \frac{1}{2} m_e (\dot{X}_i)^2 \quad (16)$$

In the case of shear failure mode, instead of Eqn (12) and (14) we will have Eqn (17) and (18) as follows:

$$\delta = \frac{\tau_{\max} L^3}{3 E' h^2} \quad (17)$$

$$V_s = \frac{2}{9} \frac{\tau_{\max}^2 b L^3}{E' h} \quad (18)$$

In deriving the above equations, implicitly a generalized vibration shape has been assumed, which is,

$$\psi(x) = 3\left(\frac{x}{L}\right) - 4\left(\frac{x}{L}\right)^3 \quad \text{for } x \leq \frac{L}{2} \quad (19)$$

Based on this assumed shape, m_e is,

$$m_e = 2\bar{m} \int_0^{L/2} \psi^2 dx = 0.486 \bar{m} L \quad (20)$$

where \bar{m} is the mass of the beam per unit length.

COMPARISON WITH THE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The integrity of the results obtained by the proposed solution was compared with the experimental results of Ref. [2]. Table 1 shows the details of the composites which were experimentally examined by this reference. The impact tests were performed with unnotched specimen on an instrumented Tinius-Olsen impact testing machine. The capacity of this machine was 358 J with a 4.9 m/s striking velocity of the hammer. The span length for all specimens was fixed at 40 mm. Table 2 shows the static and impact test results of the specimens that are tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of the specimens used for impact testing by reference 2

Prepreg	Resin	Fiber	Symbol
HY-E-9034C	Fiberite 934	E-glass unidirectional	E
HY-E-1734A	Fiberite 934	Kevlar-49	P
HY-E-1034C	Fiberite 934	Thornel-300	T
CE-9006/GY-70	Ferro CE-9006	GY-70	G
CE-9006/PRD 49	Ferro CE-9006	Kevlar-49	K

From Ref. [2]

Table 2. Static and impact characteristics of unidirectional fiber composites

Symbol	Static			Impact				
	L/h	σ_{\max} GPa	E' GPa	L/h	σ_{\max} GPa	U_t J	u_t KJ/m ²	u_i KJ/m ²
E	15.8	1.64	46.9	16.1	1.94	18.98	621.6	466.2
T	14.6	1.57	108.3	14.6	1.58	6.51	186.9	85.7
G	12.8	0.66	123.5	12.6	0.48	0.47	12.3	12.3
P	17.6	0.59	51.8	10.5	0.69	6.92	253.3	99.5
K	11.0	0.70	37.3	10.5	0.68	12.07	238.6	76.0

From Ref. [2]

The reported values for the modulus of elasticity E' in Table 2 is a function of span to depth ratio. Shear deformation is the reason for the variation. The correction was made by using Eqn (21) and the corrected values are tabulated in column 3 of Table 3.

$$E = \frac{E'}{1 - 1.2 \left(\frac{h}{L}\right)^2 \frac{E'}{G}} \quad (21)$$

The total energy absorbed in impact is the sum of the fracture initiation and the propagation energy and is shown by U_t . This value was then divided by the specimen cross section area (b.h)

to obtain the unit total energy (u_t). The last three columns of Table 2 show the total energy, unit total, and unit initiation energy, respectively.

Table 3. Calculated properties of the specimens

Symbol	G, GPa	E, Gpa	h, mm	b, mm	ρ , kg/m ³	E^* , GPa
E	3.24	50.4	2.48	12.3	2100	47.0
T	2.67	140.3	2.74	12.7	1600	108.3
G	2.14	213.9	3.17	12.1	1700	121.8
P	1.69	58.8	3.81	7.2	1400	42.6
K	1.69	47.8	3.81	14.8	1400	36.5

* This value is calculated by Eqn (13) for L/h ratio of samples in dynamic case which differs from those in static case

Table 3 shows other required properties for our analysis which were deduced from the reference. All the parameters required for the dynamic analysis were normalized for 1m width of specimens and are tabulated in Table 4. Since the L/h ratio of all specimens were high, it was believed that the failure would begin in flexural mode. Therefore, Eqn (14) through (16) were used for calculating the absorbed energy. The unit energy corresponding to strain, damping and inertia are tabulated in column 7, 8, and 9 of Table 5, respectively.

In order to determine the damping energy, it is necessary to know the value of material's damping ratio ξ . This material property is not available for the materials used in Ref. [2], therefore, certain assumption has to be made. It is assumed that $\xi = 0.01$ which is in good agreement with the experimental results of 0° glass-epoxy reported in Ref. [3]. The reference reports the damping ratios for various modes and amplitudes of vibration. Free vibration decay measurement method was used for measuring the damping ratio. It was discussed earlier that the beam subject to impact will respond under the first mode. Therefore, only the results corresponding to the first mode of vibration are used. It has been reported that the damping ratio of material subjected to larger amplitude and lower number of cycles is higher. Under impact situation the amplitude is so high that the deflection of specimen never reaches to the amplitude of vibration and the specimen breaks much sooner (within a quarter of a cycle). Therefore, it is expected that the values of damping ratio to be considerably larger than the highest reported value in this reference (i.e., 0.9%).

Table 4. Calculated parameters for 1m width of specimens

Symbol	m_w , kg	m_e , kg	k, N/m	ω , rad/s
E	2424	0.10	4.505×10^7	136.3
T	2348	0.09	1.392×10^8	243.5
G	2465	0.10	2.436×10^8	314.4
P	4142	0.10	1.472×10^8	188.5
K	2015	0.10	1.261×10^8	250.2

The comparison between the values of u_i of Table 2 and those of Table 5 shows a close agreement for specimens T and G. However, the difference for specimens E, P and K are noticeable. Nevertheless, inspection of the load-time graph of some of the specimen as shown in Fig. 4 reveals the presence of a nonlinear response in these specimens before the load reaches to the maximum value. The points corresponding to the onset of nonlinearity are marked on the graphs. The corresponding time and energy of these points are in very good agreement with the calculated results.

Table 5. Calculated values at the instant of failure initiation

Symbol	δ_{\max} m	t_i sec	\dot{X}_i m/sec	F_S kN	F_D kN	V_S kJ / m ²	V_D kJ / m ²	V_i kJ / m ²	$V_{total}=u_i$ kJ / m ²
E	4.43×10^{-3}	8.99×10^{-4}	4.851	199.57	32.05	178.	57.8	0.47	236.2
T	1.42×10^{-3}	2.89×10^{-4}	4.881	197.66	55.81	51.2	29.0	0.39	80.59
G	0.33×10^{-3}	0.68×10^{-4}	4.897	80.63	75.90	4.2	7.9	0.38	12.48
P	1.13×10^{-3}	2.29×10^{-4}	4.891	166.34	76.37	24.8	22.7	0.31	47.81
K	1.30×10^{-3}	2.64×10^{-4}	4.883	163.93	49.24	28.1	16.9	0.31	45.31

Figure 4. Load and energy history of the specimens in impact test. From Ref. [2].
(Top-left): Thornel-300, (Top-right) E-glass, (Bottom) Kevlar-49.

Figure 5. Comparison of FEM analysis with SDOF solution

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Damping force of laminated composites subjected to impact loading has been calculated and reported in Table 5. The magnitude of this force is comparable with F_s (the force that corresponds to the strain energy), and has significant effect on the magnitude of the energy absorbed during impact. Damping force increases as the velocity of the striker increases and is also related to the mass of striker. However, since the variation of damping ratio with respect to the striker's mass is not clear, a definite conclusion on this matter at this juncture is not possible.

It is believed that the damping force is distributed between resin and fibers based on their damping properties. Thus, the constituent having the higher damping ratio would have more influence. Therefore, one may expect premature failure of fibers in composites consisting of fibers with high damping ratio. Amongst the five composites that were examined (see table 2), specimen G hosted GY-70 carbon fiber which is known to possess high damping property[4]. Based on the experimental results presented in Table 2, it is believed that a premature failure for this specimen is inevitable.

On the other hand, in specimens consisting of fibers with low damping and resin with high damping, it is expected that the major portion of damping force to be absorbed by resin. In this case premature breakage of fibers will not occur and shear failure (of resin) might be dominant. Debonding and delamination which are very common phenomenon in impact can be considered as the effects of shear failure caused by damping force. Therefore under the impact loading the total energy as the result of delamination and debonding is expected to be higher than the total energy under static loading condition.

The validity of the SDOF assumption was examined by conducting a finite element analysis (FEM). The results of this analysis for specimen E, having the lowest stiffness, and specimen G, having the highest stiffness amongst the examined samples, are plotted in Figure 5. The corresponding solution based on our assumption is also presented. An excellent agreement between FEM analysis and the proposed solution can be seen in the figure.

It is acknowledged that the effect of damping on the response of composites under impact loading deserves further consideration. Meanwhile, based on the presented work, the following conclusions can be made.

- 1- Damping effect can significantly influence the energy absorbent capacity of composites.
- 2- The force corresponding to the damping can be high and might have significant effect on the mode of failure.
- 3- The effect of inertia in energy absorbing capacity is negligible.
- 4- The energy absorbed during impact depends on the velocity and the mass of striker.

REFERENCES

1. R. W. Clough and M. J. Penzien, Dynamics of Structures, McGraw-Hill, Inc. 41- 46 (1975).
2. P. K. Mallick and L. J. Broutman, Static and Impact Properties of Laminated Hybrid Composites, Journal of Testing and Evaluation, Vol. 5, (May 1977), 190-200
3. A. B. Schultz and S. W. Tsai, J. Composite Materials, Vol. 2, No. 3 (July 1968), 368-379
4. P. K. Mallick, Fiber Reinforced Composites; material, manufacturing and design, New York, NY, Marcel Dekker, Inc., 301,(1993)